

Kullback-Leibler Entropy and Quantum Average Momentum

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The Kullback-Leibler entropy is defined as: $-\int dx P(x) \ln \{ P(x)/R(x) \}$ where $P(x)$ and $R(x)$ are two classical probability distributions i.e. real, positive functions with values between 0 and 1. In (1), it is shown that the Kullback-Leibler entropy is equivalent to Fisher's information if $R(x) = P(x+\delta x)$ where δx is a tiny constant. We argue that in this case, the Kullback-Leibler entropy represents either average momentum multiplied by spatial density in a quantum bound state, i.e. $\int dx W(x)W(x) \{dW/dx / W\}$ which is 0 because overall the particle does not move in one direction (odd function). This suggests forwards and backwards internal motion which yields 0 overall translation, similar to fluctuations (in x not t). In addition, it represents the "fluctuations" or average momentum for half the classical probability distribution associated with a quantum free particle $\exp(ipx)$, namely $C \cos(px) \cos(px)$. Again the Kullback-Leibler entropy for this distribution (or $\sin(px)\sin(px)$) is 0. (This is equivalent to the result of a particle in an infinite potential well if one considers $\cos(px)$, the wavefunction.)

Thus a statistical quantity, namely Kullback-Leibler entropy, seems to be associated with quantum mechanical motion (average momentum). This motion is linked with zero Kullback-Leibler entropy where $P(x)$ is a distribution and $R(x)=P(x+\delta x)$. Furthermore, this seems to show, we argue, that d/dx in Fisher's information is linked with physical momentum.

Quantum Free Particle

A quantum free particle travels with constant speed and momentum in a certain direction. If one wishes to assign a classical probability $P_{\text{classical}}(x)$ to each x , then $P_{\text{classical}}(x)=\text{constant}$. This probability scheme, however, loses information, namely p (momentum), and so is the same for any p . It would be good to have a distribution $P(x)$ which accounts for the information p . This cannot be created for a real, positive function $P(x)$ such that it maps into $P_{\text{classical}}(x)=\text{constant}$, but it can be done for a pair of real functions ($f_1(x), f_2(x)$) such that $f_1(x)f_1(x) + f_2(x)f_2(x) = 1$.

We note that $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. This anticipates the form used in Fisher's information, i.e. $d/dx \exp(ipx) / \{ \exp(ipx) \}$ although we note that Fisher's information only applies to classical probabilities (i.e. real, positive and between 0 and 1). $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)\sin(px)$, however, may be used to construct Fisher's information. In such a case:

$$I(\cos(px)\cos(px) + I(\sin(px)\sin(px)) = \text{constant} \quad ((1))$$

$$I = \text{Fisher's information} = \int dx P(x) \{d/dx \ln(P)\} \{d/dx \ln(P)\} \quad ((2))$$

((1)) holds for the integrand of Fisher's information i.e. each x point has the same weight even though two related probability distributions are used. It would be interesting to associate a type of entropy with the distributions $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)\sin(px)$. The Kullback-Leibler entropy expression seems suitable because it uses two classical probability functions $P(x)$ and $R(x)$ i.e.

$$G = \text{Kullback-Leibler entropy} = - \int dx P(x) \ln\{ P(x)/R(x) \} \quad ((3))$$

$\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)\sin(px)$, however, will not be compared, but rather $P(x)$ and dP/dx because for motion in a single direction, one is interested in a probability distribution and its change. One may note that:

$$d/dx \{ \cos(px)\cos(px) \} = -2p \cos(px) \sin(px) \quad \text{and} \quad d/dx \{ \sin(px)\sin(px) \} = 2p \cos(px) \sin(px) \quad ((4))$$

Thus the sum of changes $dP1/dx + dP2/dx = 0$ for $P1=\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and $P2=\sin(px)\sin(px)$. The change of one compensates the change of the other so that each x point has the same weight which is $P1+P2$. This seems to suggest a kind of internal periodic motion in each of the two functions which allows the particle to move along with a constant p as if simply translating in x space, even though $P1(x)$ and $P2(x)$ show more complicated x space dependence.

The fact that $P(x)$ and dP/dx are not the same shows that two probability distributions are needed to move through space with constant p . This idea also holds for $\exp(ipx)$. $-d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ shows that motion through space does not alter the base square-root probability, but only involves the information p .

We argue that analysis is usually done at the $\exp(ipx)$ level, but there also exists the classical level i.e. $\exp(ipx) \exp(-ipx)$ and one may apply statistical quantities at this level. This is why we examine $P(x)$ and dP/dx where $P(x)$ is a classical type probability. In reality, $\exp(ipx)$ means that $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ work together and so one performs calculations using $\exp(ipx)$ as in a 2-slit interference problem. For a bound state, however, one calculates the real wavefunction, but may then consider the physical spatial distribution $W(x)W(x)$ and think of it in terms of statistical quantities. That is what we try to do in this note.

Kullback-Leibler Entropy and Fisher's Information

In (1) it is shown that one may write the discrete form of Fisher's information in a way in which it is equivalent to Kullack-Leibler entropy for a particular $R(x)$. The discrete form of Fisher's information is:

$$I \text{ discrete} = \text{Sum over } i \ (1/\delta x) \ \{ P(x_{i+1}) - P(x_i) \} \ \{ P(x_{i+1}) - P(x_i) \} / P(x_i) \quad ((5))$$

Given that the Kulback-Leibler entropy is expressed in terms of logarithms, one must introduce \ln . This may be done for tiny values present using (from (1)):

$$\ln(1+g) = g - gg/2 \quad \text{where} \quad g = P(x_{i+\delta x})/P(x_i) - 1 \quad \text{taken from } ((5))$$

In (1) (see details there) it is then shown that ((6)) becomes:

$$I \text{ discrete} = -2/\delta(x) \ \text{Sum over } i \ P(x_i) \ \ln \{ P(x_{i+\delta x}) / P(x_i) \} \quad ((6))$$

((6)) may be written in integral form: $-\frac{2}{\Delta x} \int dx P(x) \ln \left\{ \frac{P(x+\Delta x)}{P(x)} \right\}$ ((7))

((7)) is in the form of Kullback-Leibler entropy with $R(x) = P(x+\Delta x)$.

$-\frac{2}{\Delta x} \int dx P(x) \ln \left\{ \frac{P(x+\Delta x)}{P(x)} \right\}$ and Its Relationship to Average Quantum Bound Momentum

We consider the case of a quantum bound state for which $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, which is real, because the particle is localized, i.e. the center-of mass is not translating. Writing $P(x+\Delta x)$ as $P(x) + (\Delta x) \frac{dP}{dx}$ to first order:

$$-\frac{2}{\Delta x} \int dx P(x) \ln \left\{ \frac{P(x+\Delta x)}{P(x)} \right\} = -\frac{2}{(\Delta x)} \int dx P \ln(1 + (\Delta x) \frac{d \ln P}{dx})$$

$$= -\frac{2}{\Delta x} \int dx P(x) \frac{d}{dx} \ln(P) = -\frac{4}{\Delta x} \int dx W \frac{dW}{dx} \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is proportional to the average internal quantum momentum multiplied by quantum spatial density. This integrates to 0 (as it is an odd function and one integrates from -infinite to infinite). In other words, there is internal momentum, but it has positive and negative regions because overall the system does not translate. Thus the Kullback-Leibler entropy is also 0.

In other words, we argue that the average physical internal momentum fluctuations (dependent on x not t) are associated with a type of entropy, namely Kullback-Leibler entropy, and this is zero for a bound state. Thus, quantum dynamics (within a bound state) (albeit using classical type probabilities i.e. $W(x)W(x)$) may be associated with an entropy.

$-\frac{2}{\Delta x} \int dx P(x) \ln \left\{ \frac{P(x+\Delta x)}{P(x)} \right\}$ and Its Relationship to a Quantum Free Particle

A quantum free particle, as noted above, is represented by a kind of square root probability $\exp(ipx)$ such that $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$. In other words, it consists of two classical probability distributions $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)\sin(px)$. If one considers one of these and its x derivative i.e. $P(x)$ and $\frac{dP}{dx}$, then ((8)) becomes (for $P = \cos(px)\cos(px)$):

$$C1 \int dx \cos(px) (-p \sin(px)) \quad ((9)) \text{ which again equals 0 (for the same reason as above)}$$

$\cos(px) (-p \sin(px))$ is again the average momentum associated with $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$ multiplied by its density. This is an internal average momentum which creates motion.

$$\text{For } \exp(ipx), \text{ the average momentum of the particle is: } p \frac{\exp(ipx)}{\exp(ipx)} = p \quad ((10))$$

((9)) is not the same as ((10)). ((10)) considers the free particle as a whole (i.e. both of the necessary functions $\cos(px)$, $\sin(px)$ are required for motion in one direction. ((9)) considers $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ by itself, associating it with a classical-like density of $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and an average momentum of $-p \sin(px)/\cos(px)$. This is equivalent to the Kullback-Leibler entropy and is 0. Thus there seems to be a kind of entropy associated with each component $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. One may note that this entropy also appears in the case of a particle in a well with infinite potential walls. In such a case one only has 2 $\cos(px)$ (even case about origin). The Kullback-Leibler entropy which integrates to 0 then describes the entropy of the $\cos(px)$ piece i.e. $P(x)=\cos(px)\cos(px)$.

We further argue that these examples show that d/dx which appears in Fisher's information and is used to create $R(x)=P(x + \delta x)$ is ultimately associated with physical momentum which may be measured by noting the impact of an impulse.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that in (1) it is shown that Kullback-Leibler entropy ((3)) for $P(x)$, $R(x)$ being two classical probability distributions is equivalent to Fisher's information if $R(x) = P(x+\delta x)$. We show that this Kullback-Leibler entropy integrates to 0 and represents spatial density $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$ (where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}$) multiplied by average momentum $dW/dx / W$ for a quantum bound system. In other words, a quantum bound system does not translate (is localized), but it does have internal momentum which fluctuates in sign with x , but integrates to 0. Given the result of (1), this is identical to having a zero entropy, albeit the Kullback-Leibler entropy with $R(x)=P(x+\delta x)$. Fisher's information is defined in terms of d/dx acting on $P(x)$, so we argue that d/dx ultimately represents physical momentum in a problem. We also note that for $V(x)=0$ i.e. a potential with infinite walls, $P(x)=\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and the Kullback-Leibler entropy is 0 again. This is equivalent to the integral of spatial density: $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ multiplied by average momentum $d\cos(px)/dx / \cos(px)$.

We point out that for a free particle with $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$, overall momentum = $-i d/dx \exp(ipx) / \exp(ipx)$, but if one considers each function, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ separately in terms of classical-like probabilities $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)\sin(px)$, then Kullback-Leibler entropy is 0 for each function i.e its average momentum multiplied by its density is 0 when integrated. For a quantum free particle, however, one must consider $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ working together at the $\exp(ipx)$ (wavelength level) because they describe how a particle moves. Thus it is $\exp(ipx)$ which is used in analysing two slit interference etc.

At the classical probability level, however, $\cos(px)\cos(px) + \sin(px)\sin(px) = 1$ so one may calculate an average momentum for each classically i.e. $\text{Integral } \cos(px)\cos(px) d/dx \cos(px) / \cos(px)$ and a similar quantity for $\sin(px)$. These both are 0 and represent 0 Kullback-Leibler entropy. Thus at the classical level, (modulus $\exp(ipx) = 1$), one does not see the internal fluctuations in x of average momentum multiplied by density. The particle simply translates with constant p and 0 Kullback-Leibler entropy through space. In particular, a classical particle with constant p would be said to have 0 entropy. (These conclusions, however, exist using classical type analysis i.e. $\cos(px)\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)\sin(px)$ separately, and not the combination of

$\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ working together at the quantum wavefunction level which is required to solve various physical problems (2-slit interference, 1-dimensional reflection/refraction etc).

References

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